

varietal release committee in 1985 as TPS1. This is the first variety released from the Thirupathisaram PES, Tamil Nadu.

TPS1, a derivative of IR8/ Kattisamba, is semitall (110 cm), matures in 110-115 d, and has higher

yield potential than local Kattisamba. It is medium tillering with light green foliage and good panicle exertion. Panicles are long and compact.

Average grain yields of 5.0 t/ha, 17.8% more than those of Kattisamba, have been recorded. Production

potential is 7.8 t/ha. Average straw yield is 9.2 t/ha. The grain is short bold with a red kernel closely resembling that of Kattisamba. It possesses good cooking quality.

TPS1 has field tolerance for stem borer. □

Rice variety resistant to gall midge (GM) and bacterial blight (BB) released in Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

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Usha, a semidwarf high yielding rice variety with resistance to GM and BB, has been released for general cultivation in MP. Usha is derived from IR22/W1263. It resembles IR22 in plant type. IR22 is susceptible to GM and BB but Usha and W1263 are

Table 1. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of TN1 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction			
	F ₁	F ₂		
		Resist ant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)	χ^2 3:1
TN1/Usha	Resistant	671	245	1:40
TN1/W1263	Resistant	287	113	2.08

resistant at Raipur, MP. A single dominant gene *GMI* conferred Usha's resistance to the GM biotype.

A single dominant gene also conferred resistance to BB (Table 1). Usha and W1263 have the same allelic gene *Xa-4* as IR22 has (Table 2).

Table 2. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of IR22 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction		
	F ₁	F ₂	
		Resistant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)
IR22/Usha	Resistant	856	0
IR22/W1263	Resistant	406	0

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Influence of vegetative growth duration on grain grade

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The vegetative growth (VG) period of BPI-76, a photoperiod-sensitive cultivar, was altered to 45, 65, 85, and 105 d by manipulating photoperiod. Plants were grown in 4-liter plastic pots in the glasshouse. Each pot contained 3.5 kg soil fertilized with 4 g ammonium sulfate, 2 g solophos, and 2 g muriate of potash. Five plants per pot were grown under 24-h photoperiod. Sowings were staggered.

Plants were transferred to 10-h photoperiod so that climatic conditions during reproductive and ripening phases were similar. Grain grade was determined by the specific gravity method.

Grain yield was higher with 45 and 65 d VG (see table) and gradually

Influence of vegetative growth duration on number of different grades of grain per hill.^a IRRRI, 1986.

Parameter	Vegetative growth duration			
	45 d	65 d	85 d	105 d
Grain yield/hill (g)	6.8 a	6.2 a	5.4 b	4.4 c
Panicles/hill	3.8 a	3.1 b	2.7 c	3.1 d
Total spikelets	459 a	429 ab	381 bc	336 c
Empty spikelets	54 a	72 a	70 a	74 a
	(11)	(16)	(18)	(22)
Poor grains ^b	46 a	44 a	34 a	24 a
	(8)	(10)	(9)	(7)
Average ^b	157 a	115 a	42 b	38 b
	(28)	(32)	(10)	(11)
Good ^b	200 a	198 a	233 a	193 a
	(49)	(41)	(66)	(59)
High density grains ^b	1.5 a	1.0 a	2.2 a	0.7 a
	(4)	(2)	(5)	(3)
Total grains	405 a	358 b	311 c	262 d
	(89)	(84)	(83)	(78)

^aFigures in parentheses are percent of respective grades of total spikelets. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bPoor grains = collected from 1.0-1.06 specific gravity; average grains, 1.08-1.12 specific gravity; good grains, 1.14 to 1.10 specific gravity; and high density grains, 1.20 specific gravity.

decreased with increased growth duration. The higher grain yield at 45 and 65 d was due mainly to high panicle numbers, fertility percentage, and total grain numbers per hill.

High density (HD) grain yield (grains which submerge at 1.20 sp gr) was not related to VG duration. BPI-76 produced hardly any HD grains; production of HD grain did not differ